

Performance Evaluation of Cooperative Diversity in Flat Fading Channel with Error Control Coding

Authors : Oluseye Adeniyi Adeleke, Mohd Fadzli Salleh

Abstract : Cooperative communication provides transmit diversity, even when, due to size constraints, mobile units cannot accommodate multiple antennas. A versatile cooperation method called coded cooperation has been developed, in which cooperation is implemented through channel coding with a view to controlling the errors inherent in wireless communication. In this work we evaluate the performance of coded cooperation in flat Rayleigh fading environment using a concept known as the pairwise error probability (PEP). We derive the PEP for the various cases in coded cooperation and then compare with the signal-to-noise ratios of the users in the network. Results show that an increase in the SNR leads to a decrease in the PEP. We also carried out simulations to validate the result.

Keywords : channel state information, coded cooperation, cooperative systems, pairwise-error-probability, Reed-Solomon codes

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